

Handling Public Complaints Via the Online Dumas Presisi at the Police Supervision Inspectorate in West Kalimantan

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ABSTRACT: Although the Dumas Presisi (Precision Public Complaints) Online system has been implemented, this problem persists because of the continued public complaints about the handling of complaints that are perceived as slow, less transparent and unresponsive. The purpose of this study is to describe and analyze the implementation process of the policy of handling public complaints through online Precision Public Complaints at the Sub-Division of Public Complaints of the West Kalimantan Police Supervisory Inspectorate with the stages of organization, interpretation and application. The method employed was descriptive with a qualitative approach and data collection techniques were in the form of interviews, observation and documentation. The results indicate that Online Precision Public Complaints policy implementation has a clear organizational structure in the implementation, but is not optimal in cross unit coordination and personnel. However, there are still many obstacles to the policy implementation, including limited human resources, low digital literacy of the public and less than optimal program socialization. However, the Police institution considers this system as a step towards transparency and accountability in public service. This research recommended that to achieve effective and efficient service goals, the capacity of policy implementers should be strengthened, supporting infrastructure improved and the community should be actively involved in the complaint process.

KEYWORDS: Handling Public Complaints, Public Complaints, Dumas Presisi (Precision Public Complaints)

INTRODUCTION

Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia National Police Number 9 of 2018 concerning Procedures for Handling Public Complaints within the Republic of Indonesia National Police and followed up by the issuance of Circular Letter of the Chief of Police Number: SE/5/II/2021 dated February 24, 2021 concerning the Integrated Information System for Handling Public Complaints within the National Police, this policy emerged as a response to the need to increase the accountability and transparency of the police institution in carrying out its duties and functions, with the aim of increasing the accountability of the Republic of Indonesia National Police (Polri) in carrying out its duties. Public complaints against the actions of Polri members who are unprofessional or deviate from ethical standards and procedures must be handled properly and transparently. With this regulation, Polri can demonstrate its commitment to self-improvement and be more open to criticism and input from the public.

The policy development process aims to realize the concept of "Precise Police" (Predictive, Responsible, and Transparency with Justice), as the National Police needs a clear system for handling public complaints. This regulation serves as a legal basis for ensuring that public complaints (Dumas) are handled promptly, transparently, and fairly, ultimately increasing public trust in the National Police. Therefore, it requires alignment with developments in society, science, technology, and laws and regulations, as stipulated in Article 13 of Law Number 2 of 2002 concerning the National Police of the Republic of Indonesia.

The West Kalimantan Regional Police Supervisory Inspectorate, which has five personnel (1 Pamen, 3 Pama, and 1 Bintara), with this number of personnel, it is certainly not comparable to the number of public complaints that continues to increase every year, coupled with limited budget support of IDR 19,919,000 per year and is also not comparable to the area of the West Kalimantan Regional Police which includes 14 Regional Police Units. Based on data on the number of public complaints in 2022 to 2024 which has increased, so it is necessary to complete professional, objective and accountable public complaint handling services. To find out the data on the number of public complaints in 2022 - 2024 based on Dumas sources, it can be seen in table 1.1 below.

Based on table 1.1, it shows that the number of public complaints has increased every year, namely throughout 2022 to 2024 as many as 43 complaints, with details of 2022 to 2023 as many as 23 complaints and 20 complaints from 2023 to 2024. According to the classification of public complaints grouping, the majority of public complaints received are related to the case investigation process carried out by the National Police, as data in 2022, namely 40 complaints out of a total of 67 complaints, in 2023 as many as 65 complaints out of a total of 90 complaints and finally in 2024 as many as 84 complaints out of a total of 110 complaints.

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Table 1.1: Public Complaints Based on Dumas Sources 2022 – 2024

No	Sources of Dumas	Number of Dumas per year		
		2022	2023	2024
1	ITWASUM POLRI	6	12	19
2	KOMPOLNAS RI	8	29	25
3	KEMENSEKNEG RI	-	-	3
4	KEMENKUMHAM RI	1	2	-
5	OMBUDSMAN RI	8	7	-
6	KOMNAS HAM RI	3	3	3
7	LBH / ADVOKAT	5	4	8
8	LSM	2	2	1
9	MASYARAKAT	34	31	51
Jumlah		67	90	110

Sources: Subbag Dumas Inspektorat Pengawasan Polda Kalbar, Jan 2025

The increase in public complaints against the Indonesian National Police (Polri) is caused by various factors, including those related to the professionalism of police officers, inadequate service quality, negative perceptions of the police, dissatisfaction with the legal process and workload, and a lack of resources. Furthermore, increased access to information and technology, namely the rapid development of information technology and social media, has made it easier for the public to submit complaints or grievances about the performance of the Polri. Platforms such as Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, and other applications allow the public to report incidents or actions that do not meet expected standards, whether in the form of violations by Polri officers or dissatisfaction with the services provided. This easy access facilitates the public to be more open in expressing their complaints.

METHOD

This research uses a descriptive research type with a qualitative approach. According to Moleong (2013:29), descriptive research is "describing phenomena that occur in the field as they are, then drawing conclusions, in order to obtain a theory and prioritizing the process rather than the results." Then Faisal (2010:12) states that descriptive research is "research in which there are efforts to describe, record, analyze and interpret current conditions.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. Online Organizational Stage of Dumas Presisi

Organizationally, in accordance with Indonesian National Police Regulation Number 14 of 2018 concerning the Organizational Structure and Work Procedures of Regional Police, the Indonesian National Police (Polri) has a detailed organizational structure for carrying out its duties and functions. This regulation establishes how the organization within the Regional Police (Polda) is structured and operates, with the aim of ensuring the effective and efficient implementation of police duties. This organizational structure consists of various levels and units that coordinate with each other, starting from the Regional Police (Polda) and the Resort Police (Polres) down to the Polsek (Sub-district Police).

This regulation also regulates the division of duties, authority, and responsibilities between each unit within the Polri organization, thus supporting the achievement of the police's primary objectives, namely maintaining security, order, and law enforcement throughout Indonesia. Understanding the structure and work procedures in this regulation is crucial for every Polri member to carry out their duties in accordance with applicable regulations and to create synergy between various units in achieving common goals.

In the context of the online Dumas Presisi (Electronic Public Complaint System), the West Kalimantan Regional Police Inspectorate manages and responds to public complaints received through the platform. This system allows the public to report problems or complaints related to police services and actions more easily and transparently, with the aim of increasing the accountability and responsiveness of the National Police in responding to public complaints. The complaint process is managed by Itwasda, which functions to ensure that each complaint is followed up in accordance with applicable procedures and ensures fair and transparent resolution. Based on the results of an interview with the Head of the Dumas Sub-Division of the West Kalimantan Regional Police Supervisory Inspectorate, Dumas Inspectorate of the West Kalimantan Regional Police, stated that organizationally the mechanism for implementing the policy of handling public complaints through the online Dumas Presisi at the West Kalimantan Regional Police Supervisory Inspectorate (Kalbar) has several important stages and steps. In resolving complaints handling in the form of an explanation of the results of clarification and follow-up received by the reporter with a time limit of no later than 20 working days, as stipulated in the Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia National Police Number 9 of 2018.

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This statement indicates that the organizational mechanism for implementing the public complaints handling policy through the Dumas Presisi online system at the West Kalimantan Regional Police Supervisory Inspectorate includes: Complaint Channels: The public can submit complaints through the Dumas Presisi online platform provided by the West Kalimantan Regional Police, such as the mobile app or the official website, www.dumaspresisi.go.id, which can be downloaded from the Play Store or App Store. Furthermore, complaints can be reports of alleged violations, abuse of authority, or complaints about public services by police officers.

An interview with the Head of the Dumas Sub-Division of the West Kalimantan Regional Police Supervisory Inspectorate stated that the rationale behind the issuance of the Dumas Presisi online system was to increase the effectiveness, efficiency, and transparency in handling public complaints. Prior to the online system, the public experienced difficulties or obstacles due to complicated administrative procedures or long distances. With the Dumas Presisi platform, With precision, the public can easily file complaints from anywhere and at any time, without having to go directly to the police station. One of the main reasons for this policy is to create a more transparent system for handling complaints. With a recorded and organized platform, every complaint received can be clearly monitored, processed, and followed up. This reduces the likelihood of complaints being handled inappropriately or in a non-transparent manner. Every complaint is recorded in the system, allowing authorities to monitor each stage of the resolution process. This ensures that every action taken is accountable to the public.

In response to this statement, it can be assumed that the reason for issuing the policy for handling public complaints through the online Dumas Presisi at the West Kalimantan Regional Police Supervisory Inspectorate is to increase the effectiveness, efficiency, transparency, and accountability in handling public complaints. This policy aims to make it easier for the public to submit complaints online, without being limited by time and distance. It ensures that every complaint is handled openly, clearly, and can be monitored, thereby minimizing the potential for abuse of authority. It makes the police more responsible in handling complaints and improves the image of the National Police in the eyes of the public by demonstrating a commitment to good and professional service. It accelerates the process of processing and resolving complaints by using technology, which allows for faster and more structured follow-up. In addition, it provides an easier channel for the public to participate in monitoring police performance and encourages active participation in maintaining the integrity of the West Kalimantan Regional Police institution.

Based on interviews with members of the public who submitted online complaints through Dumas Presisi, they stated that the complaint standards are quite clear, with easy-to-understand instructions, allowing us as reporters to submit reports without technical obstacles. However, these complaint standards must be accompanied by a clear estimated follow-up time so that we know when the complaint will be further processed. Furthermore, complaint follow-up must be carried out in accordance with established standards, ensuring that complaints are not only responded to administratively but also resolved substantively and adequately.

Based on these statements, it can be concluded that the public expects a complaint handling policy that is fast, transparent, accountable, and efficient. These standards include ease of access, speed of response, transparency of information, and fair and timely resolution of problems. Furthermore, data security and clear communication between the police and the complainant are also considered crucial in maintaining public trust in this complaint system. Therefore, one of the standards the public desires is assurance that their personal data submitted through the Dumas Presisi platform will be properly protected and will not be misused.

Based on observations and documentation, it shows that the organizational process related to the implementation of the public complaint handling policy through the Dumas Presisi online system at the West Kalimantan Regional Police Supervisory Inspectorate includes several important steps to ensure the smoothness and effectiveness of the system, by determining the main objectives of the public complaint handling policy, such as increasing transparency, accountability, and better service to the public. Developing a clear and structured Standard Operating Procedure (SOP): on how complaints will be received, processed, and followed up by the relevant parties. In addition, forming a team responsible for the implementation of this policy, including personnel from various units such as information technology, legal, and supervision. By following this organizational process, it is hoped that the implementation of the public complaint handling policy through the Dumas Presisi online at the West Kalimantan Regional Police Supervisory Inspectorate can run effectively and efficiently.

2. Interpretation/Understanding Stage of the Online Dumas Presisi

The interpretation stage in the implementation process of the public complaints handling policy through the online Dumas Presisi at the West Kalimantan Regional Police Supervisory Inspectorate is a crucial step aimed at ensuring that the implemented policy is well understood by all parties involved, both internally at the West Kalimantan Regional Police and by the public who use the complaint service. The implementation process begins with understanding and interpreting the objectives, targets, and procedures contained in the online Dumas Presisi policy. Decision-makers and policy implementers at the West Kalimantan Regional Police Supervisory Inspectorate need to understand the context of this policy, such as efforts to increase transparency, accountability, and speed in responding to public complaints.

Interpretation also leads to adapting the policy to the actual needs of the community. This includes understanding the types of complaints most frequently received, the desired response time for the public, and the type of feedback the public expects regarding their complaints. Submit. Policy interpretation here also relates to how relevant and responsive the system is to expectations and

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realities on the ground. At the interpretation stage, it is also important to ensure that the implemented policy is consistent with the long-term goals of the West Kalimantan Regional Police Supervisory Inspectorate of improving public services and more transparent supervision. Based on the results of an interview with the Head of the Dumas Sub-Division of the West Kalimantan Regional Police Supervisory Inspectorate, Dumas of the West Kalimantan Regional Police Supervisory Inspectorate stated that one effective way to provide understanding of the policy for handling public complaints through the online Dumas Presisi is through direct socialization and education to the public. One form of socialization carried out is by holding workshops at the community or community organization level that allows information to reach the public directly. These training and workshops are very effective ways to provide public understanding on how to use the online Dumas Presisi system. This training not only provides technical understanding on how to access and fill out the complaint form, but also explains the complaint handling process and the public's rights in the process.

Then the results of the interview with the Head of the Dumas Sub-Division of the Inspectorate of the West Kalimantan Regional Police Dumas Inspectorate of the West Kalimantan Regional Police also provided information that the implementation of the socialization of the public complaint handling policy through the Dumas Presisi online platform has been carried out according to SOP standards, with the aim of making it easier for the public to submit complaints regarding police services, while increasing transparency and accountability in handling public reports. The implementation of this socialization is not only carried out through various media, but also through direct activities, such as training and counseling to the public on how to use the platform. This aims to ensure that the public has a sufficient understanding of this system and can utilize it optimally.

The interview results indicate that the process of implementing the socialization of the public complaint handling policy through the online Dumas Presisi by the Dumas Sub-Division of the Supervisory Inspectorate of the West Kalimantan Regional Police, we need to examine several aspects related to the process. One of the policies implemented by the National Police, especially in the West Kalimantan Regional Police, is to provide convenience for the public in submitting complaints online. This system aims to facilitate public access in submitting complaints or reports regarding services or actions taken by police officers. The main objective is to accelerate the complaint handling process and increase transparency and accountability of the National Police in handling existing problems in the community through the online platform provided by the West Kalimantan Regional Police.

3. Dumas Presisi Online Application/Implementation Stage

The Dumas Presisi (Presisi Public Complaints Management) application/implementation policy is a significant innovation introduced by the West Kalimantan Regional Police, through the Dumas Sub-Division of the Supervisory Inspectorate, to improve accountability and transparency in handling public complaints. Dumas Presisi is an online platform that allows the public to submit reports or complaints regarding police actions or security issues in a simpler, faster, and more transparent manner. This application provides a platform for the public to submit complaints or information related to police services directly and without any obstacles.

The implementation of this policy aims to provide easier access to complaints services for the public and to increase the effectiveness of complaint handling by incorporating technology into the report submission and follow-up process. Dumas Presisi utilizes digital technology to connect the public with law enforcement officials, enabling each complaint to be followed up more quickly and in accordance with established procedures. However, the implementation of this policy is not without challenges, both in terms of public outreach, the use of technology, and in ensuring the quality of complaint handling.

Based on the results of the interview with the Head of Dumas Sub-Division of the Inspectorate of the West Kalimantan Regional Police, Dumas Inspectorate of the West Kalimantan Regional Police, stated that: the first stage in implementing this policy is regarding the existence and working methods of Dumas Presisi. Socialization is carried out through various channels, such as: Social media (Facebook, Instagram, Twitter), the official website of the West Kalimantan Regional Police, Direct counseling through activities involving the community and collaboration with local institutions and community leaders. Although there have been various socialization channels, we acknowledge that there are parts of society that are less exposed to this information, especially those in remote areas or who are not familiar with digital technology. This is an obstacle in ensuring that all levels of society can utilize this platform optimally.

Responding to the statement, it shows that the application/implementation stage of the public complaint handling policy through the online Dumas Presisi by the Dumas Sub-Division of the Inspectorate of Supervision of the West Kalimantan Regional Police shows a strong commitment to increasing transparency and accountability in public services. However, there are several challenges that need to be overcome, such as limited accessibility for people in remote areas, the need for further training for officers, and strengthening coordination between agencies. With continuous evaluation and improvements on the technical and operational side, Dumas Presisi can be more effective in providing complaint handling services to the public. Again, the Head of the Dumas Sub-Division of the Inspectorate of the West Kalimantan Regional Police, Dumas Inspectorate of Supervision of the West Kalimantan Regional Police, stated that: the first step we took was socialization and counseling to the public about the existence of the Dumas Presisi platform. This aims to increase public awareness about the importance of complaints and how to report problems through the online system.

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To ensure this information reaches all levels of society, especially those living in remote areas, the Dumas Sub-Division conducts direct outreach using various media, including local radio and leaflets/brochures. We recognize that despite these outreach efforts, some communities still lack access to technology or are not covered by digital outreach channels. Therefore, they are working to expand the reach of outreach through various methods.

This statement can be seen in the implementation of the public complaint handling policy through Dumas Presisi by the Dumas Sub-Division of the Inspectorate of the West Kalimantan Regional Police Supervision involves various strategic steps to ensure that this system runs effectively. The steps taken include broader socialization, simplification of complaint procedures, increasing officer capacity, efficient verification, and regular monitoring and evaluation. Although there are several challenges faced, such as limited access for some communities and long processing times, improvements are continuously being taken to increase the effectiveness of Dumas Presisi in providing services to the public.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the description of the research results and discussion presented in the previous chapter, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- a. The organizational or institutional stage in the implementation of the public complaint handling policy through the Dumas Presisi online complaint handling platform is still suboptimal due to limited personnel and budget support, as well as the vastness of West Kalimantan, which are obstacles.
- b. The interpretation or understanding stage in the implementation of the public complaint handling policy through the Dumas Presisi online complaint handling platform appears to be uneven among the public. This is due to the lack of broad and comprehensive outreach, which has resulted in the public having difficulty fully understanding how to use the Dumas Presisi online complaint platform.
- c. The application or implementation stage in the implementation process of the public complaint handling policy through the online Dumas Precise has been running and implemented, but has not been optimal regarding technological accessibility, especially in areas with limited internet infrastructure.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on these conclusions, this study offers the following recommendations:

- a. Improvements in the organizational stage require the support of competent personnel and adequate budgetary support to ensure objective and accountable follow-up actions in handling complaints submitted to the public through the Dumas Presisi online application.
- b. Improvements in the Interpretation/Understanding stage require widespread and comprehensive public outreach, particularly through various social media platforms, brochure distribution, and direct outreach through National Police personnel. This ensures the public understands and comprehends the procedures and mechanisms for submitting complaints through the Dumas Presisi online application accurately and correctly.

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